

Case Report

The performance of hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix during immediate single-tooth implant placement in the aesthetic zone

Serhat Aslan ^{1, 2*} , Sive Ercan Aslan ¹

¹ Private Practice Dr. Serhat Aslan, İzmir, 35220, Turkey

² Department of Biomedical, Surgical and Dental Sciences, University of Milan, Milan, 20122, Italy

* Correspondence: perio@drserhataslan.com

Abstract: The immediate single-tooth implant placement in the aesthetic zone represents a clinical challenge for preserving the bone contour. Aim of this clinical case was to observe the effect of grafting the buccal bone gap during immediate implant placement. The buccal bone gap was filled with a new hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix to preserve the mucosal contour. At re-entry surgery, partial preservation of the buccal bone wall was observed after 6 months of healing and stable peri-implant bone was present. Such treatment during immediate single-tooth implant placement in the aesthetic zone may provide buccal contour stability.

Keywords: aesthetics; dental; immediate implant placement; tooth socket

Published: 20.12.2022

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56939/DBR221041a>

Introduction

In the era of aesthetics, replacement of the missing tooth with dental implants requires sufficient hard and soft tissue dimensions to protect the natural emergence of the restoration [1]. To reduce the negative outcomes of the tooth loss, different treatment modalities have been proposed so far [2-6]. However, to the date, dimensional preservation of outer bony walls have not been demonstrated yet [7-10]. Considering of these aspects of dimensional changes following tooth loss, flapless immediate implant placement seems to provide some benefits to patient and clinician [11, 12]. For instance, in the presence of buccal bone wall, flapless surgery without sutures brings an advantage of intact vascular supply for buccal bone and reduces the side effects of flap surgery by minimal tissue trauma [13]. Also, with the primary stability of implant, there is a possibility to fabricate an implant-supported provisional restoration [14]. The use of provisional restoration maintains aesthetic appearance of the patient, and may help to guide soft tissue healing following tooth extraction [15-17].

To protect the volume of the immediate implant site, different treatment concepts have been proposed so far. Grafting the gap between implant and buccal bone wall using bone substitute biomaterials has been tested in several clinical studies [18-20]. This approach may help to minimize patient morbidity while preserving soft tissue contours. To date, various biomaterials have been tested in clinical studies, however, none of them demonstrated the use of hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix to fill the buccal bone gap. More specifically, this matrix is a sponge-

like biomaterial composed of 80% microparticulate hydroxyapatite alloplast graft and 20% sugar cross-linked porcine type 1 collagen, which has already proven to be successful in ridge preservation [21].

The aim of this clinical report was to assess and demonstrate the effect of filling the buccal bone gap using a new hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix during immediate implant placement. We achieved that after 6-months uneventful healing as there was no penetration of the periodontal probe in the previous buccal bone gap.

Materials and Methods

A 42-year-old female patient referred to the dental practice, requesting the esthetic replacement of upper left central incisor (Fig. 1a). The tooth had suffered from palatal perforation due to several attempt and unsuccessful endodontic treatment. Following the discussion of the treatment plan, the patient decided upon immediate implant placement and provisionalization, then gave her written informed consent. The patient was a light-smoker and systemically healthy. Radiographic examination using cone beam computed tomography revealed a pathology due to palatal perforation and 0.8 mm buccal bone thickness (Fig. 1b).

Figure 1. Initial clinical situation: (a) Tooth replacement requirement in the esthetic zone; (b) Palatal perforation and 0.8 mm buccal bone thickness.

The surgical site was disinfected prior to extraction with a 0.12% chlorhexidine digluconate solution. Following the extraction, bone sounding with UNC-15 periodontal probe (Hu-Friedy, Chicago, IL, USA) confirmed the presence of intact thin buccal bone plate (Fig. 2a, 2b). Implant osteotomy was initiated engaging two-thirds of the palatal bone to provide the ideal 3-dimensional position and high primary stability (Fig. 2c).

Figure 2. Tooth extraction: (a) Extraction procedure; (b) Intact thin buccal bone; (c) Implant osteotomy.

Then 4.2x13 mm implant (AstraTech EV, Dentsply Sirona, Germany) was inserted and positioned 4 mm apical to the prospective mucosal margin (Fig. 3a, 3b).

Figure 3. Implant placement: (a) Implant insertion; (b) Final implant position.

Consequently, the remaining gap between the buccal bone and the implant was grafted with the hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix made by GLYMATRIX® core technology (Ossix™ Bone, 5x10x10 mm, Datum Dental Ltd, Israel) [21]. Prior to filling the gap, the matrix was hydrated using the bleeding from the extraction socket followed by size adaptation (Fig. 4a, 4b).

Figure 4. Bone grafting procedure: (a) Matrix insertion; (b) Final matrix position.

Following the digital impression, design and milling, a non-functional CAD-CAM screw-retained provisional was tightened at 15 Ncm of torque onto the implant (Fig. 5a, 5b, 5c).

Figure 5. Screw-retained provisional being installed

At the end of the surgery, patient received an analgesic (Brufen 600 mg, Abbott Laboratories, UK) and was instructed to take a subsequent dose 8 hours later. To control bacterial contamination, patient was prescribed systemic antibiotic (Augmentin BID 1000 mg, GlaxoSmithKline, UK) during the first post-operative week. The patient was asked to refrain

from brushing the surgical site for the post-operative 2-week period but to rinse with 0.12% chlorhexidine digluconate for 1 min twice daily. The patient was advised to follow a soft diet and avoid functioning at the implant site.

Results

At 1-week, the surgical site healed without any complications and only a slight oedema was noticed in the buccal aspect. Anyway, after an uneventful healing of 6-months, a crown lengthening surgery was performed to create harmonious gingival margin levels (Fig. 6a). During the surgery, partial preservation of the buccal bone wall was observed and there was no penetration of the periodontal probe in the previous buccal bone gap (Fig. 6b). After 3-months of soft tissue maturation, individually fabricated zirconia abutment luted to the titanium base was tightened at 25 Ncm of torque onto the implant. Afterward, definitive zirconia crown was cemented. Patient was fully satisfied regarding esthetics of the implant restoration and harmonious gingival margins (Fig. 6c).

Figure 6. Follow up and satisfactory final outcome: (a) Uneventful healing after 6-months and crown lengthening surgery; (b) Partial preservation of the buccal bone wall; (c) Definitive zirconia crown was cemented after 3 months of soft tissue maturation.

Discussion

This clinical report confirms that filling the buccal bone gap using a hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix in immediate implant placement and provisionalization is able to maintain the natural appearance of buccal contour without any adverse events. The overall outcome of this case was a success in terms of aesthetics and function.

Implant-supported restoration in the aesthetic zone is a great challenge and affected by several elements such as timing of implant installation, alveolar socket morphology, soft and hard tissue dimensions, clinical skills, implant position and prosthetic design. The aesthetic failures in immediate implantation are questioning the time of placement

[22-23]. Therefore, the concept of early implant placement has been suggested as from the patient's perspective, it requires additional surgical procedures and seems more costly when compared to immediate implant placement [24].

Filling the buccal bone gap with biomaterials in combination with immediate implant placement has the potential to preserve the natural appearance and can be considered minimally invasive as it does not require flap reflection or second-stage surgery, periosteal release, autogenous bone scraping and barrier membrane [25]. However, minimally invasive tooth extraction and implant positioning are technique-sensitive and require surgical expertise to maximize the aesthetic outcome. In this particular case, it is interesting to observe the buccal bone remnants during the second stage surgery. It may be speculated that flapless surgery and gap filling might help to observe this phenomenon.

Recently, Casarez-Quintana and co-workers compared the histological wound healing and ridge dimension changes using 90% bovine-derived xenograft granules in a 10% porcine collagen matrix and sponge-like matrix of 80% microparticulate hydroxyapatite alloplast graft with 20% sugar cross-linked porcine type 1 collagen [21]. The hydroxyapatite-sugar crosslinked collagen matrix yielded statistically significantly more vital bone compared to xenograft matrix due to its synthetic nature, which has much faster biodegradation time. However, ridge dimension changes were similar between two groups and were found adequate for implant placement, which not necessarily guarantees the long-term effect. The benefit of providing more vital bone cannot be justified in short-term studies and requires long-term results and scientific evidence.

It should be highlighted that the buccal bone thickness of the present case was measured 0.8 mm at baseline and was classified as thin bone phenotype. To compensate the missing bone gap, a collagen containing matrix has been used that can be easily adjusted to the defect volume. Here the synthetic hydroxyapatite has the function of maintaining the volume stability while the collagen contributes for faster cells proliferation [25]. A partial preservation of the buccal peri-implant bone was observed after 6 months of healing. The osseointegration process was uneventful and enabled the delivery of zirconia crown installation with custom abutment (Fig 6).

Conclusions

Maintaining the natural appearance and buccal bone continuity is a challenging task with immediate implant placement. Within the limits of this report, buccal contour stability can be obtained by filling the bone gap using a hydroxyapatite-sugar cross linked collagen matrix in immediate implant placement. This technique requires high surgical skills and further clinical studies with long-term results.

Funding and conflict of interest statement: The authors claim no conflict of interest and there was no funding for this case.

Board review and informed consent statement: The local authorities allow publication of such cases after the patient gives a written informed consent.

References

- [1] U. Grunder, S. Gracis, and M. Capelli, "Influence of the 3-D bone-to-implant relationship on esthetics," *The International journal of periodontics & restorative dentistry*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 113-9, Apr 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/15839587>.
- [2] Y. Miyamoto and T. Obama, "Dental cone beam computed tomography analyses of postoperative labial bone thickness in maxillary anterior implants: comparing immediate and delayed implant placement," *The*

- International journal of periodontics & restorative dentistry, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 215-25, Jun 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21556378>.
- [3] S. Aslan, "Improved volume and contour stability with thin socket-shield preparation in immediate implant placement and provisionalization in the esthetic zone," *The international journal of esthetic dentistry*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 172-183, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29687096>.
- [4] M. B. Hurzeler, O. Zuhr, P. Schupbach, S. F. Rebele, N. Emmanouilidis, and S. Fickl, "The socket-shield technique: a proof-of-principle report," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 855-62, Sep 2010, doi: 10.1111/j.1600-051X.2010.01595.x.
- [5] D. Baumer, O. Zuhr, S. Rebele, and M. Hurzeler, "Socket Shield Technique for immediate implant placement - clinical, radiographic and volumetric data after 5 years," *Clinical oral implants research*, vol. 28, no. 11, pp. 1450-1458, Nov 2017, doi: 10.1111/clr.13012.
- [6] M. Stefanini, P. Felice, C. Mazzotti, M. Marzadori, E. F. Gherlone, and G. Zucchelli, "Transmucosal Implant Placement with Submarginal Connective Tissue Graft in Area of Shallow Buccal Bone Dehiscence: A Three-Year Follow-Up Case Series," *The International journal of periodontics & restorative dentistry*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 621-30, Sep-Oct 2016, doi: 10.11607/prd.2537.
- [7] L. Schropp, A. Wenzel, L. Kostopoulos, and T. Karring, "Bone healing and soft tissue contour changes following single-tooth extraction: a clinical and radiographic 12-month prospective study," *The International journal of periodontics & restorative dentistry*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 313-23, Aug 2003. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12956475>.
- [8] M. G. Araujo and J. Lindhe, "Dimensional ridge alterations following tooth extraction. An experimental study in the dog," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 212-8, Feb 2005, doi: 10.1111/j.1600-051X.2005.00642.x.
- [9] D. Botticelli, T. Berglundh, and J. Lindhe, "Hard-tissue alterations following immediate implant placement in extraction sites," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 31, no. 10, pp. 820-8, Oct 2004, doi: 10.1111/j.1600-051X.2004.00565.x.
- [10] V. Chappuis, O. Engel, K. Shahim, M. Reyes, C. Katsaros, and D. Buser, "Soft Tissue Alterations in Esthetic Postextraction Sites: A 3-Dimensional Analysis," *Journal of dental research*, vol. 94, no. 9 Suppl, pp. 187S-93S, Sep 2015, doi: 10.1177/0022034515592869.
- [11] J. Cosyn, A. Eghbali, H. De Bruyn, M. Dierens, and T. De Rouck, "Single implant treatment in healing versus healed sites of the anterior maxilla: an aesthetic evaluation," *Clinical implant dentistry and related research*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 517-26, Aug 2012, doi: 10.1111/j.1708-8208.2010.00300.x.
- [12] J. Y. Kan, K. Rungcharassaeng, M. Ojano, and C. J. Goodacre, "Flapless anterior implant surgery: a surgical and prosthodontic rationale," *Pract Periodontics Aesthet Dent*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 467-74; quiz 476, Jun-Jul 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/11405003>.
- [13] F. Raes, J. Cosyn, E. Crommelinck, P. Coessens, and H. De Bruyn, "Immediate and conventional single implant treatment in the anterior maxilla: 1-year results of a case series on hard and soft tissue response and aesthetics," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 385-94, Apr 2011, doi: 10.1111/j.1600-051X.2010.01687.x.
- [14] S. Raes et al., "Oral health-related quality of life changes after placement of immediately loaded single implants in healed alveolar ridges or extraction sockets: a 5-year prospective follow-up study," *Clinical oral implants research*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 662-667, Jun 2017, doi: 10.1111/clr.12858.
- [15] J. Cosyn, L. Pollaris, F. Van der Linden, and H. De Bruyn, "Minimally Invasive Single Implant Treatment (M.I.S.I.T.)

- based on ridge preservation and contour augmentation in patients with a high aesthetic risk profile: one-year results," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 398-405, Apr 2015, doi: 10.1111/jcpe.12384.
- [16] J. Pitman, L. Seyssens, V. Christiaens, and J. Cosyn, "Immediate implant placement with or without immediate provisionalization: A systematic review and meta-analysis," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 49, no. 10, pp. 1012-1023, Oct 2022, doi: 10.1111/jcpe.13686.
- [17] L. Seyssens, A. Eghbali, and J. Cosyn, "A 10-year prospective study on single immediate implants," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 1248-1258, Oct 2020, doi: 10.1111/jcpe.13352.
- [18] J. Cosyn, A. Eghbali, A. Hermans, S. Vervaeke, H. De Bruyn, and R. Cleymaet, "A 5-year prospective study on single immediate implants in the aesthetic zone," *Journal of clinical periodontology*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 702-9, Aug 2016, doi: 10.1111/jcpe.12571.
- [19] J. Cosyn et al., "Four modalities of single implant treatment in the anterior maxilla: a clinical, radiographic, and aesthetic evaluation," *Clinical implant dentistry and related research*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 517-30, Aug 2013, doi: 10.1111/j.1708-8208.2011.00417.x.
- [20] A. Eghbali, H. De Bruyn, T. De Rouck, R. Cleymaet, I. Wyn, and J. Cosyn, "Single implant treatment in healing versus healed sites of the anterior maxilla: a clinical and radiographic evaluation," *Clinical implant dentistry and related research*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 336-46, Jun 2012, doi: 10.1111/j.1708-8208.2010.00283.x.
- [21] A. Casarez-Quintana, B. L. Mealey, G. Kotsakis, and A. Palaiologou, "Comparing the histological assessment following ridge preservation using a composite bovine-derived xenograft versus an alloplast hydroxyapatite-sugar cross-linked collagen matrix," *Journal of periodontology*, Jun 4 2022, doi: 10.1002/JPER.22-0149.
- [22] D. Buser, M. M. Bornstein, H. P. Weber, L. Grutter, B. Schmid, and U. C. Belser, "Early implant placement with simultaneous guided bone regeneration following single-tooth extraction in the esthetic zone: a cross-sectional, retrospective study in 45 subjects with a 2- to 4-year follow-up," *Journal of periodontology*, vol. 79, no. 9, pp. 1773-81, Sep 2008, doi: 10.1902/jop.2008.080071.
- [23] D. Buser et al., "Early implant placement with simultaneous guided bone regeneration following single-tooth extraction in the esthetic zone: 12-month results of a prospective study with 20 consecutive patients," *Journal of periodontology*, vol. 80, no. 1, pp. 152-62, Jan 2009, doi: 10.1902/jop.2009.080360.
- [24] D. Buser, V. Chappuis, M. M. Bornstein, J. G. Wittneben, M. Frei, and U. C. Belser, "Long-term stability of contour augmentation with early implant placement following single tooth extraction in the esthetic zone: a prospective, cross-sectional study in 41 patients with a 5- to 9-year follow-up," *Journal of periodontology*, vol. 84, no. 11, pp. 1517-27, Nov 2013, doi: 10.1902/jop.2013.120635.
- [25] J. Y. K. Kan, K. Rungcharassaeng, M. Deflorian, T. Weinstein, H. L. Wang, and T. Testori, "Immediate implant placement and provisionalization of maxillary anterior single implants," *Periodontology 2000*, vol. 77, no. 1, pp. 197-212, Jun 2018, doi: 10.1111/prd.12212.